

APPARENT MOLAL VOLUMES OF ELECTROLYTE MIXTURES IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION.

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The variation of apparent molal volume (ϕ) of an electrolyte with concentration is governed by the relation : $\phi = \phi_0 + k \sqrt{C}$ (at least for concentrations greater than 0.03 M) where ϕ_0 and k are constants. The apparent molal volume of a mixture of electrolytes at any concentration can be calculated as in the case of a single electrolyte, if the average molecular weight of the mixture is calculated from the mixture rule. It is found (a) that a mixture of electrolytes also obeys the above equation with the same limitations as a single electrolyte, and (b) that both ϕ_0 and k in case of mixtures are linear functions of the composition (molar percentage of any one of the components).

The apparent molal volumes of strong electrolytes were shown empirically to vary linearly with the square root of concentration by Masson (*Phil. Mag.*, 1929 vii, 8, 218) and Geffcken (*Naturwiss.*, 1931, 15, 321 ; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, 155, 1). Redlich and Rösenfeld deduced the same result from the interionic attraction theory (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, 155, 65). Their equation may be written as

$$\phi = \phi_0 + k \sqrt{C},$$

where ϕ denotes the apparent molal volume, ϕ_0 and k are constants characteristic of the solute and temperature. Redlich and Rösenfeld's theory predicts that the value of k should be the same for all strong electrolytes of the same valence type at extreme dilution. This, however, has not been borne out by the results of Srinivasan and Prasad (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1939, 35, 1462) as well as by the data of Jones and Ray (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 187) incorporated by the former authors in their paper. They find that the values of k of electrolytes of the same valence type are not the same, though generally of the same order. The square root law is also not strictly valid at extreme dilutions. Similar observations were made by the present authors with electrolytes of the 2-1 valent type (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1939, 35, 1466). So far the case of mixtures of strong electrolytes has not engaged the attention of workers. The apparent molal volume of any mixture of two strong electrolytes may be calculated from the usual formula,

$$\phi = \frac{M}{\rho_0} - \frac{1000(\rho - \rho_0)}{\rho_0 C},$$

where M is the average molecular weight of the solute, C , the total concentration of solute, ρ and ρ_0 , the density of solution and water respectively. The average molecular weight, M of a mixed solute composed of electrolyte 1 of

molecular weight M_1 and electrolyte 2 of molecular weight M_2 in the molar ratio n_1 to n_2 can be readily obtained from the formula,

$$M = \frac{n_1 M_1 + n_2 M_2}{n_1 + n_2}$$

In case $n_1 : n_2$ is kept constant and the total concentration is varied, the average molecular weight is fixed.

It would be of interest to examine if the apparent molal volume (of solutions in which $n_1 : n_2$ is kept constant) thus obtained would follow the law : $\phi = \phi_0 + k\sqrt{C}$ and if it did, how the constants ϕ_0 and k would vary with composition and how they would be related to the values for the pure components. To clarify these points, apparent molal volumes of two mixtures with a common ion (K_2SO_4 and KCl ; $NaNO_3$ and $NaCl$) and two without a common ion ($NaNO_3$ and KCl ; $NaNO_3$ and HCl) were determined. Three different compositions were studied in each case. The constants ϕ_0 and k for pure K_2SO_4 and HCl were also determined. The values for pure KCl , $NaNO_3$ and $NaCl$ were taken from Srinivasan and Prasad's paper (*loc.cit.*).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The thermostat which was maintained at $35^\circ \pm 0.005$ has already been described (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 12, 499 ; 1938, 15, 301). The procedure for density determination is the same as that described in the latter paper, except that the pyknometers used had volumes of about 64 and 55 c.c. and all the weights were reduced to vacuum standard by means of the formula,

$$W_v = W + (V_1 + V_p - V_w)\rho$$

where ρ is the density of air, W_v , the weight in vacuum, W , the weight in air, V_w , V_1 and V_p , the volumes of weights, liquid and pyknometer, the last being given by the quotient of weight of pyknometer/density of glass. The density of air was measured every day by using the formula,

$$\rho = (W_1 - W_2)/V,$$

where W_1 and W_2 are the weights of a sealed flask in vacuum and air respectively and V is its external volume (535.5 c.c.). V was found by weighing the flask in air and water without applying any buoyancy correction. In order to know W_1 , one direct determination of the density of air was made. The density figures are the results of two determinations, agreeing with each other within 1 mg. The experimental error is not expected to exceed sixteen parts in a million.

In the following table, C indicates the total concentration in gram moles per litre, ρ , the density in g. per c.c. and ϕ , the apparent molal volume in c.c. The figures for pure K_2SO_4 and HCl are given first.

TABLE I.

C .	ρ .	ϕ .	C .	ρ .	ϕ .
	K_2SO_4 . $\phi = 51.5 + 7.28 \sqrt{C}$.			HCl . $\phi = 18.2 + 1.00 \sqrt{C}$.	
0	0.994058	—	0	0.994058	—
0.0100	0.995262	54.00	0.0020	0.994087	22.09
0.0200	0.996490	52.79	0.0040	0.994127	19.33
0.0300	0.997705	52.82	0.0070	0.994170	20.58
0.0400	0.998921	52.81	0.0100	0.994233	19.61
0.0500	1.000141	52.72	0.0150	0.994315	19.44
0.0600	1.001325	53.27	0.0200	0.994949	18.75
0.0700	1.002540	53.22	0.0300	0.995834	18.81
0.2000	1.017950	54.93	0.2000	0.997657	18.58
0.5000	1.052301	56.73	0.5000	1.002854	18.98
	$[K_2SO_4] / [KCl] = 3 : 1$.			$[K_2SO_4] / [KCl] = 1 : 1$.	
	$\phi = 45.5 + 5.71 \sqrt{C}$.			$\phi = 39.6 + 4.29 \sqrt{C}$.	
0.0100	0.995100	45.24	0.0100	0.994921	38.22
0.0200	0.996115	46.60	0.0200	0.995779	40.46
0.0300	0.997165	45.89	0.0300	0.996595	39.96
0.0400	0.998176	46.51	0.0400	0.997402	40.91
0.0500	0.999205	46.53	0.0500	0.998243	40.83
0.0600	1.000232	46.56	0.0600	0.999086	40.73
0.0700	1.001254	46.65	0.0700	0.999920	40.79
0.2000	1.014351	48.01	0.2000	1.010647	41.60
0.5000	1.043934	49.72	0.5000	1.035065	42.53
	$[K_2SO_4] / [KCl] = 1 : 3$.			$[NaNO_3] / [NaCl] = 3 : 1$.	
	$\phi = 34.0 + 2.86 \sqrt{C}$.			$\phi = 27.4 + 1.00 \sqrt{C}$.	
0.0100	0.994688	36.58	0.0100	0.994565	27.84
0.0200	0.995341	35.43	0.0200	0.995055	28.69
0.0300	0.995997	34.94	0.0300	0.995560	28.48
0.0400	0.996640	35.02	0.0400	0.996064	28.38
0.0500	0.997282	35.09	0.0500	0.996569	28.32
0.0600	0.997950	34.70	0.0600	0.997095	27.92
0.0700	0.998356	34.75	0.0700	0.997628	27.54
0.2000	1.006900	35.37	0.0900	0.998601	28.06
0.5000	1.025813	36.02	0.1200	1.000144	27.82
			0.1600	1.002134	28.06
			0.2000	1.004156	28.06
			0.4000	1.014155	28.30
			0.6000	1.024202	28.30

TABLE I (contd.).

C.	P.	ϕ .	C.	P.	ϕ .
	$[\text{NaNO}_3] / [\text{NaCl}] = 1 : 1.$			$[\text{NaNO}_3] / [\text{NaCl}] = 1 : 3.$	
	$\phi = 24.4 + 1.00 \sqrt{C}$.			$\phi = 21.4 + 1.00 \sqrt{C}$.	
0.0100	0.994516	26.09	0.0100	0.994466	24.45
0.0200	0.994982	26.77	0.0200	0.994921	22.08
0.0300	0.995476	24.61	0.0300	0.995340	22.50
0.0400	0.995955	24.45	0.0400	0.995768	22.48
0.0500	0.996414	24.76	0.0500	0.996211	22.17
0.0600	0.996878	24.88	0.0600	0.996652	22.00
0.0700	0.997358	24.74	0.0700	0.997120	21.49
0.0900	0.998301	24.73	0.0900	0.997978	21.67
0.1200	0.999281	24.65	0.1200	0.999725	21.71
0.1600	1.001597	24.77	0.1600	1.001013	21.76
0.2000	1.003467	24.83	0.2000	1.002745	21.80
0.4000	1.012911	24.75	0.4000	1.011198	22.38
0.6000	1.022074	25.19	0.6000	1.019863	22.22
	$[\text{NaNO}_3] / [\text{KCl}] = 3 : 1.$			$[\text{NaNO}_3] / [\text{KCl}] = 1 : 1.$	
	$\phi = 29.7 + 1.25 \sqrt{C}$.			$\phi = 29.0 + 1.25 \sqrt{C}$.	
0.0100	0.994587	29.64	0.0100	0.994572	28.53
0.0200	0.995124	29.25	0.0200	0.995095	28.06
0.0300	0.995624	30.35	0.0300	0.995575	29.35
0.0400	0.996156	30.09	0.0400	0.996075	29.50
0.0500	0.996697	29.77	0.0500	0.996614	28.80
0.0700	0.997723	30.19	0.0700	0.997646	28.66
0.1000	0.999302	30.11	0.1000	0.999126	29.24
0.1500	1.001962	29.85	0.1500	1.001528	29.72
0.2000	1.004515	30.26	0.2000	1.004193	29.25
0.4000	1.014940	30.34	0.4000	1.014130	29.61
0.6000	1.025157	30.72	0.6000	1.024220	29.77
	$[\text{NaNO}_3] / [\text{KCl}] = 1 : 3$			$[\text{NaNO}_3] / [\text{HCl}] = 3 : 1.$	
	$\phi = 28.8 + 1.38 \sqrt{C}$.			$\phi = 28.1 + 1.00 \sqrt{C}$.	
0.0100	0.994534	29.68	0.0100	0.994470	33.15
0.0200	0.995043	28.01	0.0200	0.994926	29.64
0.0300	0.995505	29.04	0.0300	0.995397	28.40
0.0400	0.995969	29.50	0.0400	0.995865	27.86
0.0500	0.996427	28.69	0.0500	0.996301	28.17
0.0700	0.997452	29.78	0.0700	0.997193	28.25
0.1000	0.998832	29.53	0.1000	0.998532	28.29
0.1500	1.001263	29.24	0.1500	1.000738	28.50
0.2000	1.003588	29.62	0.2000	1.002948	28.58
0.4000	1.013078	29.73	0.4000	1.011717	28.89
0.6000	1.022581	29.74	0.6000	1.020517	28.99

TABLE I (contd.).

C_2	ρ_2	ϕ_2	C_1	ρ_1	ϕ_1
[NaNO ₃] / [HCl] = 1 : 1.			[NaNO ₃] / [HCl] = 1 : 3.		
$\phi = 24.6 + 1.00 \sqrt{C_2}$			$\phi = 21.5 + 1.00 \sqrt{C_1}$		
0.0100	0.994394	27.30	0.0100	0.994293	25.25
0.0200	0.994727	27.45	0.0200	0.994563	23.49
0.0300	0.995090	26.49	0.0300	0.994858	22.06
0.0400	0.995471	25.56	0.0400	0.995131	21.91
0.0500	0.995852	25.01	0.0500	0.995417	21.55
0.0700	0.996598	24.60	0.0700	0.995955	21.63
0.1000	0.997639	25.08	0.1000	0.996738	21.93
0.1500	0.999444	24.98	0.1500	0.998083	21.90
0.2000	1.001240	24.98	0.2000	0.999431	21.86
0.4000	1.008393	25.05	0.4000	1.004760	21.67
0.6000	1.015375	25.36	0.6000	1.009997	22.16

Some of the results are shown graphically in the following figure. The apparent molal volume is plotted against the square root of concentration.

The figure shows that the results are represented by straight lines. There are, however, some discrepancies at the lowest concentrations in many cases. This is in keeping with the similar observations made in this laboratory in the cases of single electrolytes (*loc. cit.*). It may be said that for concentrations greater than 0.03M, the variation of ϕ with $\sqrt{C}$ is linear, and the great sensitiveness of ϕ at low concentrations to small error in density measurements may be responsible for the discrepancies. But it is hardly likely that all these divergences, many of which are beyond experimental errors and which are almost always on the same side, are due to density errors. At any rate, above concentrations of 0.03M, the equation: $\phi = \phi_0 + k\sqrt{C}$ holds good. The discrepancies are not very glaring because very low concentrations have been avoided.

The values of the constants ϕ_0 and k are tabulated below, those for pure KCl, NaCl and NaNO₃ being taken from Srinivasan and Prasad's paper (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE II.

Solute composition.	ϕ_0 .	k .	Solute composition.	ϕ_0 .	k .
Pure K_2SO_4	51.5	7.28	Pure $NaNO_3$	30.3	1.27
$[K_2SO_4] / [KCl] = 3$.	45.5	5.71	$[NaNO_3] / [NaCl] = 3$.	27.4	1.00
$[K_2SO_4] / [KCl] = 1$.	39.6	4.39	$[NaNO_3] / [NaCl] = 1$.	24.4	1.00
$[K_2SO_4] / [KCl] = 1/3$	34.0	2.86	$[NaNO_3] / [NaCl] = 1/3$	21.4	1.00
Pure KCl	28.4	1.50	Pure NaCl	18.1	1.24
Pure $NaNO_3$	30.3	1.27	Pure $NaNO_3$	30.3	1.27
$[NaNO_3] / [KCl] = 3$.	29.7	1.25	$[NaNO_3] / [HCl] = 3$.	28.1	1.00
$[NaNO_3] / [KCl] = 1$.	29.0	1.25	$[NaNO_3] / [HCl] = 1$.	24.6	1.00
$[NaNO_3] / [KCl] = 1/3$.	28.8	1.38	$[NaNO_3] / [HCl] = 1/3$.	21.5	1.00
Pure KCl	28.4	1.50	Pure HCl	18.2	1.00

Figure 2 shows the variation of ϕ_0 and Figure 3 of k with composition.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

It is evident that the variation of both ϕ_0 and k with the composition of the mixture is approximately linear. The slight divergence may be considered well within the limits of experimental error. Thus, we can express these quantities by the simple equations: $\phi_0 = x\phi_0' + (1-x)\phi_0''$; $k = xk' + (1-x)k''$. Here, ϕ_0 and k refer to the mixture, ϕ_0' and k' to the pure first component and ϕ_0'' and k'' to the second component. "x" indicates the fractional molar concentration of the first component [$x = C' / (C' + C'')$] where C' and C'' are the concentrations of the pure first and second component respectively at a total concentration C .

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